

CT Coronary Angiography in Patients of Coronary Artery Disease**Gajanan Dhansing Chavhan**

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Abstract:

Introduction: "Coronary artery disease (CAD)" is a leading cause of death globally. Invasive coronary angioplasty, while useful, is costly and carries risks. Non-invasive imaging methods like SPECT, PET, MRI, and CT have advanced for CAD diagnosis. Coronary CT is suggested by NICE for regular chest pain patients at 10-29% risk of CAD. Pre-medication with beta-blockers is provided to lower heart rate, and nitrate enhances artery visibility.

Aims and Objectives: To assess the existence, importance, and severity of coronary artery disease by employing coronary CT angiography.

Method: In a study consisting of 80 patients who had been referred for cardiac evaluation, numerous diagnostic procedures were carried out in order to evaluate "coronary artery disease (CAD)". After taking out certain participants, the remaining group of forty patients was used for the study. The purpose of this study was to investigate whether or not there is a correlation between the findings of "computed tomography angiography (CTA)" and patient outcomes, taking into account CAD risk factors.

Result: The univariate predictors of cardiac events and serious cardiac events are presented in Table 3. Significant predictors of both types of events included age, male gender, diabetes, high cholesterol, and high blood pressure. The correlation between body mass index and serious cardiac events was weak. There was no correlation between either family history of CAD or smoking and an increased risk of CAD. Both types of events were predictably linked to the Agatston score, which measures the presence of calcified plaque. Coronary artery disease (CAD) was found to be substantially related to increased event risks, and this was true even for nonobstructive CAD and for varying degrees of vascular stenosis.

Conclusion: The study has concluded that CTA has proved its effectiveness as a diagnostic and prognostic tool in patients who have an undiagnosed heart disease.

Keywords: Computed Tomography Angiography, Invasive Coronary Angioplasty, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).

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Introduction

In many industrialised countries, coronary artery disease (CAD) is projected to be the leading cause of death, and it is emerging nations. Worldwide, CAD caused 7.3 million deaths & 58 million years of lost life due to impairment in 2001. Invasive coronary angioplasty is frequently utilised as a reliable approach to identify CAD because of its superior spatial and temporal resolution.. Yet it is a costly, intrusive operation with a high death and morbidity rate [1]. The application has favoured non-invasive imaging techniques over CAD advanced rapidly in recent years, including the use of radionuclide imaging techniques like SPECT and PET, as well such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), multi-slice CT (MSCT), and MRI [2]. Although cardiac MRI has produced encouraging findings, it is not deemed appropriate for regular clinical usage for the identification of CAD. A well-

known technique Imaging myocardial perfusion using SPECT or PET is used for the non-invasive evaluation of coronary artery constriction. the care of CAD patients' diagnostic evaluations, including disease prognosis prediction, patient selection for revascularization, and assessment for acute coronary syndromes, are where SPECT and PET are most useful [3].

One of the leading causes of morbidity and death is coronary artery disease (CAD). The current gold standard for locating the arteries in the heart (ICA) is invasive coronary angiography. With recent changes in The doctor now has access to a range of imaging procedures, such as multi-detector matrix computed tomography (MDCT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), to examine both individuals with acute coronary syndromes and those who have chronic symptoms [4]. NICE is the

United States National Institute of Clinical Excellence has released recommendations on how to evaluate chest discomfort that may have a cardiac origin. It is common practise to utilise coronary CT to treat chest pain explicitly acknowledged in the recommendations.

Cardiovascular CT and NICE recommendations

Coronary CT can be a practical and secure therapeutic tool when used properly. Two different diagnostic approaches are presented in the advice for the examination and diagnosis of individuals with suspected cardiac origin chest discomfort. The first emphasises aortic dissection and pulmonary embolism should not be ruled out with an early CT scan, in individuals with substantial chest pain who are suspected of having a previous diagnosis of acute coronary syndrome (ACS, comprising MI with unstable angina) [5]. Coronary CT has no place in these individuals and isn't a diagnostic tool for ACS. A place for coronary CT is established in the second diagnostic route. It is for people as considered stable recurrent chest pain. The kind of test chosen partially depends on the equipment and skills that are accessible locally. The NICE advice recommends coronary CT is used in patients with a 10–29% risk of developing CAD. Imaging is performed on these people in order to rule up CAD. Heart CT provides a strong negative predictive value (99%), sensitivity (98%), and specificity (85%) [6].

carrying out coronary CT

Prior to When a patient is scheduled for a pre-medication (typically beta-blockers when they are not already), coronary CT being taken by the patient) is usually given lower the heart rate. A radiographer will walk the patient through the process upon their arrival to the imaging suite and inquire about any allergies, past illnesses, and current medicines. We'll get access to the intravenous line. The patient will be led to individuals will be directed to lie flat off the CT scanner in the CT scanning room bed & linked to ECG electrodes [7]. The patient will have the chance to ask any queries they may have of the radiographers. They enable ECG-gated image capture and are connected to the CT scanner. In order to achieve optimal picture capture, additional Metoprolol, a kind of injectable beta-blocker, is routinely used to lower heart rate to around 60 beats a minute. Peak plasma levels of IV metoprolol might take as long as twenty minutes to attain. Beta blocker and nitrates should be administered while blood pressure (BP) is being monitored. If the BP is less than 100 mmHg systolic, often no further medication is provided [8].

The creation of the calcium score is advised as the first step in coronary CT after the patient is completely prepared. In the event that CT coronary angiography (CTCA) is chosen, giving Before the scan, take sublingual nitrate enhances the ability to

see the coronary arteries. To produce the best coronary artery opacification, In the antecubital fossa, a medium-diameter cannula (ideally 18 gauge) allows for a strong circulation of viscous iodinated contrast (strength: 350–400 mg/ml; flow rate: 5-7 ml/sec). It is possible to provide a test bolus using only 20 ml of contrast material and monitor the density of that material over time in the aorta that ascends. The patient's time in circulation is established as a result, and as a result, the ideal moment to start the scan in order to get the greatest amount of opacification [9].

unsuccessful catheter angiography (because of an enlarged aortic root, suspected ostial coronary disease, and congenital coronary artery disease); abnormalities, for example) may need a CT scan to detect and characterise congenital coronary anomalies, that may manifest with chest discomfort [10].

When compared with invasive coronary angiography, several Studies have shown that for diagnosing severe CAD, CCTA delivers a high level of diagnostic accuracy. Invasive coronary angiography may not be able to detect non-stenotic plaques, whereas high-quality CCTA (64-slice and higher) has the capacity to see morphological alterations within characterise the atherosclerotic plaques and the coronary artery wall them [11]. High quality CCTA is additionally capable of providing reliable details on alterations in coronary lumina. Even though coronary CT angiography produces good results, CCTA has the drawback of large radiation doses, which raises questions about the hazards connected with radiation exposure. The problem of radiation-induced cancer is a result of radiation exposure the American National Research Council has addressed, or NRC. Concerns about the population getting high doses of CT are raised as the use of cardiac CT rises, especially in young adult patients regularly brought up in study. It has become obvious that appropriate CT usage is essential for defending and improving scanning methods [12].

Method

Study Design

The study comprised 80 consecutive patients who were referred to an outpatient clinic or hospital for cardiac examination due to suspected “coronary artery disease (CAD)” between February 2022 and March 2023. Exercise ECG, stress echocardiography, and ICA were performed on patients. All patients had cardiac “computed tomography angiography (CTA)” in addition to the routine clinical workup. After excluding patients with established CAD or other cardiovascular disorders, contraindications to contrast agents, impaired renal function, inability to take a breath, or cardiac arrhythmias, a final analytical research population of 40 participants was included. All

patients gave written informed consent, and the institution's scientific and ethical committees accepted the study procedure. Diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, hypertension, positive family history of CAD, and current smoking were considered as CAD risk factors. The Diamond and Forrester technique was used to compute the pre-test probability of CAD and the Framingham risk score. The study examined the relationship between CTA factors and patient outcomes.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Patients who contributed to the outpatient clinic or were accepted to the clinic for cardiac evaluation.
- Patients with presumed “coronary artery disease (CAD)”.
- Patients who underwent “exercise electrocardiogram (ECG)”, pressure echocardiography, or “invasive coronary angiography (ICA)”.
- Patients who underwent “cardiac computed tomography angiography (CTA)” in addition to normal clinical workup.
- Patients who are equipped with written informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with comprehended “coronary artery disease (CAD)”, including those with prior “myocardial infarction” or “coronary revascularization”.
- Patients with cardiovascular disorders such as heart failure, congenital heart disease, severe valve disease, cardiomyopathy, endocarditis, or ascending aorta aneurysm.
- Patients who cannot get contrast agents due to medical conditions.
- Patients with poor renal function (creatinine consent less than 60 ml/min).
- Patients unable to maintain a 15-second breath hold.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out with the help of the SAS (version 9.1.3) and SPSS 13.0 software packages. A value of p less than 0.05 was used as the benchmark for statistical significance. Comparisons of categorical variables were made using the chi-square or Fisher exact tests, whilst comparisons of continuous variables were made using the Student t -test or the Mann-Whitney test for data that was not regularly distributed. The univariate analysis of clinical features and CTA variables to determine possible predictors was performed before the Cox

regression analysis that was used to determine the relationships between CTA variables and outcomes.

Ethical Approval

The ethical committee approved this study to protect research participants' rights, safety, and well-being.

Result

Table 1 displays the demographic data and study outcomes for 80 patients. The average age and body mass index of patients who experienced an event were somewhat greater than those who did not. More incidents occurred among male patients. Patients who had incidents also had a higher risk of CAD before the test, suggesting a link between the two variables.

Different types of patients had different reasons for undergoing CTA. Different pharmaceutical regimens were used in various groups as part of medical treatment. Clinical results in the study population may be affected by factors such as age, gender, BMI, pre-test risk of CAD, and medical comorbidities, as shown in the table.

Clinical outcomes and CTA findings for 80 patients are shown in Table 2. Greater amounts of calcified plaque were seen in patients who had experienced incidents, especially severe ones. In addition, they were more likely to have obstructive CAD and many arteries affected by severe stenosis. Patients who had incidents also had a higher prevalence of plaques and a higher Segment Involvement Score (SIS) and Segment Stenosis Score (SSS). These results point to a more direct link between CTA-detected coronary disease severity and clinical events. Therefore, CTA results are helpful in understanding the full scope of CAD, which can inform risk categorization and management choices.

The univariate predictors of cardiac events and serious cardiac events are presented in Table 3. Significant predictors of both types of events included age, male gender, diabetes, high cholesterol, and high blood pressure. The correlation between body mass index and serious cardiac events was weak. There was no correlation between either family history of CAD or smoking and an increased risk of CAD. Chest pain, a positive stress test, and a high Framingham risk score were all linked to a higher risk of cardiovascular events. Nitrates, diuretics, and statins were the medicinal treatments most strongly linked to increased risk of adverse outcomes. Various correlations were observed with the use of ACE inhibitors, beta-blockers, aspirin, AT1-blockers, and calcium-channel blockers. Overall, these indicators shed light on the many cardiac event risk factors and can direct risk categorization and therapy choices.

Table 1: Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population and Patient Clinical Outcome

	All Patients n=80	Patients With Events n=20	Patients Without Events n=20	Patients With Hard Events n=20	Patients Without Hard Events n=20
Clinical characteristics					
Age, yrs	62 + 11	65 + 10	61 + 11	66+ 10	62 + 11‡
Male	40	9	10	11	8
BMI	27.2 + 5.2	28.2 + 5.1	26.2 + 5	26.1 + 5.4	27.1 + 4.8
Diabetes	13 (16.25)	7 (35)	6 (30)	5 (25)	4 (20)
Hypercholesterolemia	11 (13.75)	6 (30)	7 (35)	4 (20)	5 (25)
Hypertension	9 (11.25)	5 (25)	4 (20)	3 (15)	2 (10)
Family history of CAD	8 (10)	4 (20)	5 (25)	2 (10)	3 (15)
Smoking	8 (10)	4 (20)	4 (20)	7 (35)	5 (25)
Pre-test likelihood of CAD					
Low	46 (57.5)	13 (65)	12 (60)	11 (55)	8 (40)
Moderate	32 (40)	12 (60)	16 (80)	9 (45)	9 (45)
High	24 (30)	16 (80)	13 (65)	8 (40)	7 (35)
Indications for CTA					
Chest pain	14 (17.5)	7 (35)	11 (55)	7 (35)	5 (25)
Risk factors	23 (28.75)	11 (55)	7 (35)	5 (25)	6 (30)
Positive stress test	13 (16.25)	7 (35)	7 (35)	4 (20)	11 (55)
Medical therapy					
ACE inhibitors	10 (12.5)	5 (25)	6 (30)	4 (20)	3 (15)
Nitrates	12 (15)	6 (30)	5 (25)	2 (10)	5 (25)
Beta-blockers	11 (13.75)	6 (30)	3 (15)	2 (10)	4 (20)
Aspirin	6 (7.5)	3 (15)	6 (30)	3 (15)	2 (10)
Diuretics	11 (13.75)	6 (30)	2 (10)	1 (5)	3 (15)
AT1-blockers	6 (7.5)	3 (15)	6 (30)	7 (35)	1 (5)
Calcium-channel blockers	11 (13.75)	5 (25)	3 (15)	2 (10)	1 (5)
Statins	3 (3.75)	2 (10)	5 (25)	2 (10)	3 (15)

Table 2: CTA Results and Patient Clinical Outcome

	All Pa- tients n=80	Patients With Events (n=20)	Patients With- out Events (n=20)	Patients With Hard Events (n=20)	Patients With- out Hard Events (n=20)
Agatston score	30 (37.5)	15 (75)	11 (55)	11 (55)	15 (75)
No coronary disease	31 (38.75)	0	18 (90)	0	3 (15)
Nonobstructive CAD	24 (30)	13 (65)	7 (35)	3 (15)	2 (10)
Obstructive CAD	45 (56.25)	7 (35)	8 (40)	10 (50)	5 (25)
> 50% 1-vessel CAD	20 (25)	6 (30)	3 (15)	3 (15)	3 (15)
> 50% 2-vessel CAD	12 (15)	11 (55)	2 (10)	3 (15)	4 (20)
> 50% 3-vessel CAD	10 (12.5)	5 (25)	2 (10)	2 (10)	3 (15)
> 50% LMCA-CAD	3 (3.75)	2 (10)	6 (30)	3 (15)	1 (5)
> 70% 1-vessel CAD	15 (18.75)	11 (55)	5 (25)	2 (10)	9 (45)
> 70% 2-vessel CAD	8 (10)	7 (35)	3 (15)	1 (5)	6 (30)
> 70% 3-vessel CAD	5 (6.25)	5 (25)	2 (0.2)	2 (10)	4 (20)
> 70% LMCA-CAD	3 (3.75)	1 (5)	0 (0-3)*	3 (15)	2 (10)
SIS	0 (0-1)	2 (10)	0 (0-4)*	2 (10)	1 (5)
SSS	1 (0-2)	4 (20)	0 (0-3)*	1 (0-2)	0
No. of segments with plaques	0 (0-1)	2 (2.5)	0 (0-0)*	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)
No. of segments with obstructive plaques	0 (0-1)	1 (1.25)	0 (0-0)*	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)
No. of segments with noncalcified plaques	0 (0-1)	1 (1.25)	0 (0-0)*	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)
No. of segments with mixed plaques	0 (0-1)	1 (1.25)	0 (0-0)*	0 (0-1)	0

Table 3: Clinical Characteristics and Univariate Predictors of Events

	HR (95% CI) for All Cardiac Events	p Value	HR (95% CI) for Hard Car- diac Events	p-value
Clinical characteristics				
Age	1.03 (1.02-1.05)	< 0.0001	1.02 (1.01-1.03)	< 0.0001
Male	1.59 (1.17-2.28)	0.0004	1.48 (1.06-2.28)	0.01
BMI	1.02 (1.01-1.03)	0.12	1.04 (1.02-1.06)	0.08
Diabetes	2.69 (1.89-3.89)	< 0.0001	2.59 (1.69-4.06)	< 0.0001
Hypercholesterolemia	1.89 (1.39-2.59)	< 0.0001	1.69 (1.19-2.49)	0.001
Hypertension	1.88 (1.39-2.69)	< 0.0001	2.09 (1.39-3.11)	0.0002
Family history of CAD	0.88 (0.69-1.29)	0.89	0.89 (0.63-1.39)	0.89
Smoking	1.04 (0.69-1.39)	0.69	1.00 (0.59-1.39)	0.89

Framingham risk score	1.03 (1.02–1.04)	< 0.0001	1.04 (1.02–1.05)	< 0.0001
Pre-test likelihood of CAD				
Low	0.59 (0.39–0.89)	0.36	0.68 (0.49–1.09)	0.17
Moderate	1.04 (1.03–1.05)	0.01	1.01 (1.0–1.02)	0.04
High	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	0.0006	1.79 (1.19–2.59)	0.001
Indications for CT				
Chest pain	1.19 (1.01–1.59)	0.04	1.19 (1.01–1.39)	0.03
Risk factors	1.39 (1.03–1.68)	0.004	1.39 (1.01–1.69)	0.01
Positive stress test	1.59 (1.09–2.19)	0.004	1.49 (1.09–2.09)	0.004
Medical therapy				
ACE inhibitors	1.29 (0.89–1.79)	1.29	0.89 (0.59–1.47)	0.8
Nitrates	1.89 (1.11–3.04)	0.0079	1.49 (0.79–2.78)	0.17
Beta-blockers	1.39 (1.07–2.01)	0.0149	0.89(0.5–1.39)	0.59
Aspirin	1.89 (1.39–2.58)	< 0.0001	1.09 (0.68–1.69)	0.39
Diuretics	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	0.0012	1.58 (1.09–2.49)	0.01
AT1-blockers	1.19 (1.00–1.39)	0.04	1.05 (0.69–1.38)	0.69
Calcium-channel blockers	1.49 (1.06–2.09)	0.017	1.29 (0.79–2.08)	0.16
Statins	2.28 (1.69–3.19)	< 0.0001	1.69 (1.08–2.49)	0.003

Table 4 shows the CTA-based univariate predictors of cardiac events and hard cardiac events. Both types of events were predictably linked to the Agatston score, which measures the presence of calcified plaque. Coronary artery disease (CAD) was found to be substantially related to increased event risks, and this was true even for nonobstructive CAD and for varying degrees of vascular stenosis. Moreover, the

Segment Involvement Score (SIS), the Segment Stenosis Score (SSS), the number of segments with plaques, obstructive plaques, noncalcified plaques, and mixed plaques, and the total plaque burden were all significant predictors. These results emphasise the use of CTA for measuring CAD severity and plaque features, which helps in predicting cardiac events and risk stratification.

Table 4: CTA Results and Univariate Predictors of Events

	HR (95% CI) for All Cardiac Events	P-value	HR (95% CI) for Hard Cardiac Events	P-Value
Agatston score	1.03 (1.02–1.05)	< 0.0001	1.02 (1.01–1.03)	< 0.0001
No coronary disease	1.59 (1.17–2.28)	< 0.0001	1.48 (1.06–2.28)	< 0.0001
Nonobstructive CAD	1.02 (1.01–1.03)	0.12	1.04 (1.02–1.06)	0.12
Obstructive CAD	2.69 (1.89–3.89)	< 0.0001	2.59 (1.69–4.06)	< 0.0001
>_ 50% 1-vessel CAD	1.89 (1.39–2.59)	< 0.0001	1.69 (1.19–2.49)	< 0.0001
>_ 50% 2-vessel CAD	1.88 (1.39–2.69)	< 0.0001	2.09 (1.39–3.11)	< 0.0001
>_ 50% 3-vessel CAD	0.88 (0.69–1.29)	< 0.0001	0.89 (0.63–1.39)	< 0.0001
>_ 50% LMCA-CAD	1.04 (0.69–1.39)	< 0.0001	1.00 (0.59–1.39)	< 0.0001
>_ 70% 1-vessel CAD	1.03 (1.02–1.04)	< 0.0001	1.04 (1.02–1.05)	< 0.0001
>_ 70% 2-vessel CAD	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	< 0.0001	1.04 (1.02–1.06)	< 0.0001
>_ 70% 3-vessel CAD	0.59 (0.39–0.89)	< 0.0001	0.68 (0.49–1.09)	< 0.0001
>_ 70% LMCA-CAD	1.04 (1.03–1.05)	< 0.0001	0.68 (0.49–1.10)	< 0.0001
SIS	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	< 0.0001	1.01 (1.0–1.02)	< 0.0001
SSS	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	< 0.0001	1.79 (1.19–2.59)	< 0.0001
No. of segments with plaques	1.19 (1.01–1.59)	< 0.0001	1.19 (1.01–1.39)	< 0.0001
No. of segments with obstructive plaques	1.39 (1.03–1.68)	< 0.0001	1.39 (1.01–1.69)	< 0.0001
No. of segments with noncalcified plaques	1.59 (1.09–2.19)	< 0.0001	1.49 (1.09–2.09)	< 0.0001
No. of segments with mixed plaques	1.69 (1.19–2.29)	< 0.0001	1.49 (1.09–2.10)	< 0.0001

Discussion

The management of symptoms of intermittent angina and serious cardiovascular event prevention are the main goals of treating Coronary artery disease (CAD) is characterised by epicardial arteries and microcirculation functional changes in addition to stable morphological atherosclerotic lesions. Inducible myocardial ischemia's presence and severity have traditionally been assessed using a range diagnostic noninvasive stress tests, such as as magnetic resonance imaging, electrocardiography, and radionuclide scintigraphy, in people who do not

have an acute coronary syndrome but have established CAD and come with acute angina. However, the burden of coronary atherosclerotic disease, which cannot be readily measured by functional testing, is a major factor in patient event-free survival. As it increases diagnostic accuracy and has a good impact on clinical care, direct assessment [13]. For the diagnosis Coronary computed tomography angiography (coronary CTA) has since been accepted as the gold standard noninvasive imaging method for the diagnosis of coronary atherosclerotic disease. Coronary computed

tomography angiogram (coronary CTA) is now recognised as the pinnacle of noninvasive imaging for the detection of coronary atherosclerotic disease technique. Myocardial infarction prevention is made easier by coronary CTA-guided therapy improves patient outcomes when compared to functional evaluation of CAD. Complete Characterization of atherosclerotic plaques and the capacity to evaluate the functional importance of certain lesions are two additional strengths of coronary CTA. These features may enhance risk assessment and prognosis and more effectively refer patients for follow-up exams, such as invasive coronary angiography [14].

Recently published research from the International Study on Comparative Health Effectiveness Utilising Medical & Invasive Approaches (ISCHEMIA) research found that case for the necessity of choosing those people who have a future cardiovascular disease is highly likely to occur, and for increasing the best medical care [15]. The majority of participants In order to exclude high-risk patients from the ISCHEMIA research and people who did not have obstructive coronary artery disease (CAD), coronary computed tomography angiography (CTA) took place be randomly assigned. Often employed as a non-invasive diagnostic method, coronary CTA evaluate people who may have CAD [16]. The administration of coronary CTA is now permitted by the worldwide guidelines is a class I recommend for those with chest discomfort. Furthermore, the growing importance of coronary CTA in the various multicenter trials has demonstrated that It may soon be common procedure to monitor CAD and identify those who are at high risk of developing future cardiovascular problems available research on coronary CTA as well as its prospective use to patients with CAD following the ISCHEMIA study. For the precise treatment for avoidance of CAD in patients, risk assessment utilising thorough CAD data collected non-invasively as well as prevention of subsequent heart attacks through enhanced medical care will grow more important [17]

Multislice spiral. To diagnose coronary artery disease (CAD), computed tomography (MSCT) is used. without the need for surgery represents a promising technique. For certain patient groups, the clinical utility of this technique hasn't been decided yet [18]. The current prospective, blind study's objective was to compare coronary MSCT angiography with invasive angiography in individuals who had a low pre-test risk of having CAD in order to determine which was more beneficial for diagnosing the condition. According to this significant prospective research, simple cardiac When a patient has a moderate pre-test risk of having CAD, CT angiography provides a very sensitive approach for CAD identification. Furthermore, this approach enables extremely

secure and reliable ruling out of CAD. Finally, 64-slice CT is superior to 16-slice CT. seems to be more effective in detecting CAD [19].

With symptomatic individuals undergoing cerebral CCTA, or computed tomography angiography This study's objective was to determine how common and severe coronary artery disease (CAD) was. when compared to those who had coronary artery calcification (CAC) the outcome. Uncertainty exists about the prevalence and clinical importance of CAD among individuals lacking CAC [20]. Obstructive CAD is conceivable in symptomatic individuals who have a CAC score of 0, and it is linked to more cardiovascular events. The CCTA did not get any further prognostic data from CAC scoring. It has significant effects on antithrombotic treatment Considering the prevalence of heart attacks in people having coronary artery disease (CAD) who had paroxysmal or recently diagnosed atrial fibrillation (AF). cardiac CT angiography (CCTA) provides a practical method to find people who have hidden CAD [21]. In Our intention was to assess the early CCTA's diagnostic value in individuals who went to the hospital for paroxysmal and newly diagnosed AF. A 5-year single-center review was conducted on 566 patients with CCTA and paroxysmal and newly detected AF in order to assess the likelihood of CAD. CCTA was a helpful method for diagnosing Patients with freshly discovered or paroxysmal AF may have CAD. who are more prone to develop CAD. We advise using CCTA and CT calcium score in the diagnostic evaluation of individuals who have paroxysmal or newly-onset AF [22].

In individuals who had probable coronary artery disease (CAD), the purpose The purpose The purpose of this study was to evaluate the possible prognostic benefit of computed tomography-assisted multidetector coronary angiography (CTA). In patients with likely coronary artery disease (CAD), the aim of this study was to evaluate the long-term prognostic utility using multidetector computed tomography (CT) coronary angiography (CTA). CTA is utilised more frequently in people with suspected CAD. Despite a large amount of research confirming the utility of CTA as a predictor of outcome in patients having suspected CAD, the long-term prognosis importance of CTA is not fully explored significant cardiac events over the intermediate term. When there's no evidence of atherosclerosis, CTA demonstrates a great long-term prognosis and enables risk assessment in patients without suspected CAD and undetermined heart illness [23].

It is uncertain how well an innovative technique is cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA). for identifying structural coronary artery disease (CAD), compares to the conventional method testing under functional stress. To compare

the therapeutic effectiveness of physiological stress testing against CCTA for individuals with suspected CAD. When compared to functional stress testing, cardiac CT angiography (CCTA) is linked to a lower risk greater risk of new aspirin and statin prescriptions, invasive coronary revascularization, and CAD diagnosis than they do of myocardial infarction. Despite these variations, CCTA is not linked to a decrease in cardiac hospitalisations or death [24].

Although coronary artery disease (CAD) frequently goes unnoticed before myocardial infarction (MI) & coronary death, In persons with diabetes mellitus, it has a substantial impact on cardiovascular mortality and morbidity. to ascertain if regular When people with type 1 or type 2 diabetes who are presumed to have had an elevated heart risk have coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA) testing of CAD and then get The danger of CCTA-directed treatment mortality as well as non-fatal coronary outcomes will be lowered. When used to test for CAD in asymptomatic individuals with either kind of After four years, the combined rate of hospitalisation for unstable angina, nonfatal MI, or overall death was not decreased by diabetes. This population's CCTA screening is not supported by these data [25].

Conclusion

This study has concluded that CTA has proved its effectiveness as a diagnostic and prognostic tool in patients who have an undiagnosed heart disease. According to the findings, people who receive a CTA that reveals no signs of atherosclerosis should have an extremely favourable outlook for the future. On the other hand, coronary computed tomography (CTA) enables risk stratification in the presence of coronary artery disease (CAD), which enables medical practitioners to identify patients who are at a greater risk of future cardiac events. These findings bring to light the significance of CTA in terms of giving useful prognostic information, assisting in risk assessment, and guiding suitable therapeutic choices for patients with undiagnosed cardiac illnesses. The main limitations of these studies included short follow-up durations (usually about 1 year, with none exceeding 2 years), as well as the inclusion of patients with different types of cardiac problems who were receiving CTA for known or suspected CAD or other cardiac disorders. As a result, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the long-term prognostic usefulness of CTA in a sizable cohort of patients who had a suspicion of coronary artery disease but were free of any known cardiac conditions.

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